

Lignins as promising plant polymers for biomedical applications

Kocheva L.S.¹, Karmanov A.P.², Raskosha O.V.²

¹Institute of Geology of the Komi Science Center UB RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, karko07@mail.ru

²Institute of Biology of the Komi Science Center UB RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, apk0948@yandex.ru

Keywords: lignins, chemical structure, physiological activity

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17340851

Lignin, one of the most complex and mysterious plant polymers in terms of chemical structure, has great potential for use in various fields of practical applications. In particular, they should be considered as promising raw materials for pharmaceuticals and biomedicine. Our research is aimed at studying the relationship between the structural and chemical features of lignins of various taxonomic origin and their physiological activity.

As a result of the conducted research, a hypothesis has been put forward about the key role of natural lignins in maintaining the balance of sex hormones in the mammalian body. Preparations based on natural and technical lignin are recommended for the prevention of age-related diseases caused by excessive levels of estrogens in the body.

Stable supramolecular complexes of citrus pectin and natural lignins and water-resistant colloidal particles lignin-PVP have been developed for the production of pharmaceutical preparations. It is concluded that lignins significantly contribute to the overall antioxidant activity of plant foods. Studying the geroprotective properties of natural lignins using the example of *Drosophila melanogaster* allowed us to propose a mechanism for the oncological and geroprotective effects of lignins.

The possibility of creating effective mycotoxin sorbents based on natural lignins and nanocarbon materials obtained by carbonation of lignocellulose raw materials was shown. Effective, including universal, lignin-containing sorbents of radionuclides (uranium, radium, thorium) for aqueous media were obtained.

In vivo experiments have shown the absence of toxic effects of lignin (based on the results of comparing body weight and index values of internal organs: brain, liver, heart, kidneys, testes and adrenal glands in experimental and control groups of animals). It was found that lignin has cytotoxic activity against HeLa, A549, and HT-29 tumor cells. The cytotoxic activity of natural lignin against cancer cells can be used in the practice of cancer treatment.

There was a significant increase in the potential (by increasing the yellow bodies of pregnancy in the ovary) and actual (number of embryos) fertility of female mice who consumed a lignin solution. The study of the gerontological properties of natural lignins in mice showed a positive effect on females; the differences between the males of the experimental and control groups were not statistically significant.

The effectiveness of the chronic action of lignin has been established with the manifestation of specificity depending on the sex of the animal in assessing motor activity, research behavior, speed of tentative research reaction, emotional reactivity, as well as anxiety ("T-shaped maze" tests).

The absence of a toxic effect with prolonged use of lignin by animals, the biological efficacy and the ability to modify radiation effects indicate the prospects for further research of natural lignin as an anti-radiation agent in both acute and chronic effects of ionizing radiation.

The conducted research opens up broad prospects for the creation of new lignin-containing preparates for biomedical applications.

The study was carried out at the expense of a grant from the Russian Science Foundation № 22-13-00196-P, <https://rscf.ru/en/project/22-13-00196/>.